

A Landscape Analysis of AI Governance in India

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Executive Summary

- We are a group of researchers facilitated by Impact Academy (IA) to scope out an independent project as part of our research fellowship with IA's Future Academy
- We conducted a high-level landscape overview of India's current AI policy and strategy from an interdisciplinary perspective to put together an MVP version
- The goals of this document are:
 - To serve as a basic **reference document** on India's governance approach to AI for anyone in the AI safety community interested in learning more about the country
 - To help identify **potential levers** of change via which India can play a role in shaping the global AI governance regime
 - To inform potential areas for future **field-building** efforts in AI governance in India
- We affirm that India continues to be most important for the economy it represents, understood in terms of market size, **talent, and data**. It will also play a significant role as a leading voice from the Global South **geopolitically**, for AI safety-related international agreements as well as multilateral partnerships in the supply chain.
- During the [G20 summit in New Delhi in September 2023](#), the leaders made a Declaration regarding certain commitments, including to harness AI 'Responsibly for Good and for All'.
- India does not yet have a comprehensive legal/ regulatory framework for AI, but a new legislation to govern 'new technologies' and AI is expected after the 2024 general elections. This law, expected to be titled the 'Digital India Act', is slated to replace the current 'Information Technology Act, 2000'. In the interim, there seems to be a hybrid/ silo-based regulatory approach towards AI governance in India, which is reactive towards new information and developments. While this approach has been beneficial due to its flexibility, it has also created policy uncertainty and [confusion](#) amongst industry players regarding implementation of the ever-changing norms.
- Currently, legal issues around AI governance in India include an interest in gathering 'Indian' data to train LLMs. While access to personal data is regulated under the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, there has also been discussion around mandating Government access to 'non-personal datasets' of Indians, which are often held by private corporations. Industry advocates have pointed out legal challenges with the latter approach, including possible violation of legal commitments under both domestic as well as international copyright laws. However, others have suggested creating a 'fair use' exception to gain access to such data to train LLMs.
- The Indian government recognizes AI as a key technology for economic growth and social development and has announced a National AI Mission to boost research, skills, and adoption

- India is engaging actively in multilateral AI initiatives and could play an important role in shaping global AI governance to ensure it addresses the interests of the developing world
- Major tech companies are investing in AI R&D in India, tapping into its strengths in IT services and large talent pool
- There are also efforts to build indigenous AI capabilities, including large language models and compute infrastructure, though these are not yet at the cutting edge globally
- Key challenges for India include developing semiconductors and advanced computing infrastructure, ensuring responsible and ethical use of AI, and addressing issues of bias, fairness, and inclusion

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram of India's AI policy

General Facts

- Population: [1.438 billion](#) (2024 estimate)
- Multi-party Democracy (Quasi-federal republic with parliamentary government)
- The Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) (lit. transl. Indian People's Party) is the strongest political force
- Shares [land borders](#) with Pakistan, China, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh, and Myanmar, and [maritime borders](#) with Sri Lanka, Maldives, Indonesia and Thailand.
- With a [GDP of \\$3.5 trillion](#) (nominal) in 2022, India is the world's fifth-largest economy and is projected to be the fastest-growing major economy in the coming years
- India is a diverse, pluralistic society with many languages, religions, and cultures. Hinduism is the majority religion, followed by Islam, Christianity, Sikhism, Buddhism and others.
- Official government statistics [here](#) (in English).
- India is the most populous country in the world, has the largest youth population (66% <35 years), and will see its population rise for the next four decades. If we are living in the [most important century](#), it makes sense to focus on advanced technological (here, AI) development, deployment, and regulation that affects regions where a large portion of current and future generations (will) live. India is one such region.
- Cultural considerations:
 - According to a [survey](#) conducted by Pew Research in 2019, public opinion in India is broadly techno-optimist with a high level of trust and confidence being placed in science and technology, frequently significantly more than the global average.
 - According to [a 2023 Ipsos survey](#), urban, affluent, and/or educated Indians are polarized in their opinion about AI.
 - This segment of the population has some of the highest levels of confidence in the ability of AI to improve their lives and also some of the highest levels of anxiety regarding AI application and potential job displacement.
 - Markedly, the belief that AI will be beneficial has declined and anxiety has increased, however by a much lesser degree than in developed countries.
 - As detailed [later](#), political and public policy actors generally have a nationalistic standpoint of reducing dependence on foreign technologies and achieving self-reliance
 - **No significant talk of mitigating x-risks**

India's Role in AI Governance

Domestic Regulation

- The government think tank NITI Aayog released a 'National Strategy for AI' in 2018, articulating a vision of 'AI for All' with a focus on social sectors like healthcare, agriculture, education, smart mobility and public service delivery
- In early 2023, the government announced plans for a National AI Mission with funding support to boost AI R&D, commercialization, skills development and compute infrastructure
- An expert committee convened by the IT Ministry submitted a report in late 2023 with recommendations for India's AI strategy across 7 key areas including data, R&D, skills, funding, compute, semiconductors and governance
- Proposed approaches for AI governance emphasize:
 - Enabling innovation while instituting appropriate safeguards and risk management frameworks
 - Human control and oversight over AI systems, especially in high-stakes use cases
 - Transparency, explainability and accountability of AI models and datasets
 - Ethical principles around privacy, fairness, inclusion, and non-discrimination
 - Multi-stakeholder approaches bringing together government, industry, academia, and civil society
- Recent surveys show that the Indian public is excited about AI's potential but also wants the government to play a strong role in regulating AI to protect citizens' interests
- The upcoming [Digital India Act](#) is expected to define an overarching framework for governing digital technologies including AI
- [National Data Governance Framework](#) Policy– under which the government has asked big tech firms to share proprietary non-personal data with a centralized repository
- In 2024, the union cabinet approved a >\$10 million investment plan ([AI mission](#)) in key capabilities– startups, research, foreign collaboration, and compute.

Technological Capabilities

- India has established strengths in IT services, with a large pool of STEM graduates and software professionals. However, it lags behind the US and China in core AI research and development.
- There are increasing efforts to build indigenous AI capabilities:

- The government has proposed a National AI Research Center and is funding academic institutions and startups working on AI
- Private sector players like the Tata Group and Adani are investing in the full stack of AI, from silicon to software
- A prototype indigenous language model, 'AI4Bharat', has been developed by IIT Madras, though its capabilities are behind global leaders like GPT-3
- The telecom regulator TRAI has proposed an India-specific ChatGPT to meet local language needs and reduce dependence on foreign models
- International tech giants are also investing in AI R&D in India:
 - NVIDIA is setting up a new AI lab in Bengaluru to drive research and commercial applications
 - Microsoft, Google and Meta have engineering centers in India working on their global AI products
 - IBM, Amazon and Adobe also have substantial R&D operations tapping India's talent pool
- On AI compute, India is looking to build capacity through the National AI Mission:
 - The IT Ministry estimates that India would need compute capacity of 50-80 exaflops by 2035 to meet its AI ambitions
 - Global players like NVIDIA and AMD are partnering with Indian states, corporations and startups to set up AI computing infrastructure and data center clusters
 - C-DAC, a government R&D org, is also working to indigenously develop exascale supercomputers and AI accelerators
 - [Recently](#), India received its first major shipment of 4000 Nvidia H100 GPUs being deployed by a data center startup, Yotta Data Services, which also has further orders of nearly 16k GPUs to be delivered by June costing \$1bn.
- However, India faces a strategic vulnerability in semiconductors, being entirely dependent on imports currently. While it is looking to attract global chipmakers to set up fabs in India, the viability is uncertain given late entry, high costs and geopolitical factors. Refer to India's [National Semiconductor Mission](#).

Diplomatic and Geopolitical

- Engaged actively in multilateral initiatives to shape global AI governance

- In 2023, India [chaired](#) the Global Partnership on AI ([GPAI](#)), a multi-stakeholder initiative to support responsible AI development, where it emphasized inclusive growth and social impact ('AI For All').

Refer to GPAI [Ministerial Declaration](#) 2023, New Delhi.

- In 2023, India signed the '[Bletchley Declaration](#)' at the AI Safety Summit organized by the UK, which called for multilateral action to ensure safe and responsible development of 'frontier' AI systems. This was the first conference of its kind to elicit participation from China and Global South countries.
- India also participates in AI governance discussions at the [G20](#), OECD, UNESCO, and other multilateral fora where it voices the perspectives of the Global South

Refer OECD AI Observatory's [India profile](#)

- Multilateral relations:
 - [US \(Strategic ally\)](#): The US-India strategic partnership has been growing, with cooperation on AI R&D, skills, and governance. However, there are also economic tensions around data localization, visa policies, etc.
 - [China \(Strategic rival, trade partner\)](#): With China, India has unresolved border disputes that escalated into violence in 2020, and sees China's assertiveness and tech dominance as concerning. However, there is still substantial trade and potential for tech cooperation.
 - [Russia \(Strategic ally\)](#): trade partner for military equipment, crude oil, and gas.
 - Overall, India seeks a degree of 'strategic autonomy' in AI development while leveraging partnerships

How does this matter for AI safety?

[Abungu et al \(2023\)](#) state that the domestic governance decisions of countries like India will be important if:

1. Any of these countries builds on-premise supercomputers that can train highly capable AI
 - India's mission to create sovereign AI by harnessing its vast reserves of data and talent
 - India is currently home to 23 supercomputers. It launched a National Supercomputing Mission ([NSM](#)) in 2015 to produce supercomputer components indigenously. It currently has 4 supercomputers in the top 500 across the world, compared to China (which has 173) and the US (128).
 - NVIDIA and Reliance [announced](#) a partnership for supercomputing infra in 2023. [Earlier investments](#) by IBM and Microsoft.

- In phase I of NSM, 30 per cent of value addition was done in India, and this has been scaled up to 40 per cent in phase II. India has developed an indigenous server, Rudra.
2. Cloud-based high performance computing continues to be used to build highly capable AI, and some of the crucial data centers are in any of these countries
 - The Union Cabinet recently [approved](#) the artificial intelligence (AI) Mission under which the government will allocate funds (INR 10.3 million) towards 4 key areas: (i) AI research, (ii) funding start-ups working on designing bespoke chips for AI use cases, (iii) offering viability gap funding (VGF) for private companies looking to set up data centers in India for AI use cases, and (iv) creating compute capacity within the government.
 - India is looking to build a compute capacity of anywhere between 10,000 GPUs (graphic processing units) and 30,000 GPUs under the PPP model, and an additional 1,000-2,000 GPUs through the C-DAC.
 3. Some AI developers continue to release powerful advanced AI models open-source
 - Indigenous language models in India are not yet at the frontier
 - All well-known LLM development models right now are open source
 4. Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) remains a crucial way to train models, and any of these countries continues to be an appealing site for RLHF.
 - This seems true, given India's attractive market size, and data heterogeneity
 - Poor quality of data might be solved through synthetic data
 - Indigenous LLMs are currently being developed under institutional collaborations and public-private partnerships (See [Airavata](#))

Salient Approaches

This section is supposed to provide a more detailed overview of the policy discourse on AI in India. It is meant to be representative, not comprehensive to every stakeholder (and view– yet). However, to the best of our estimation, it captures the main intellectual efforts and viewpoints (including similarities and differences) relevant to AI policy in the country.

Government

NITI Aayog's National Strategy for AI (2018)

This was one of the first comprehensive and high-level policy outputs on the subject. The [document](#) discusses the evolution and potential of artificial intelligence (AI) and proposes an AI strategy for India. The proposed brand, #AIforAll, emphasizes inclusive technology leadership tailored to India's unique needs. The strategy focuses on sectors like **healthcare, agriculture, education, smart cities, and transportation**, aiming for economic growth and social development.

Identified barriers to AI adoption include a **lack of expertise, limited data ecosystems, high resource costs, privacy concerns, and a lack of collaboration**. To address these challenges, the strategy suggests establishing research centers, fostering international collaboration, and creating a National AI Marketplace. Skilling and reskilling the workforce are crucial, with a focus on decentralized teaching mechanisms and job creation in new areas.

The document emphasizes the government's **role as a catalyst** in supporting partnerships, providing infrastructure, fostering innovation, and ensuring ethical AI development. Key considerations for Responsible AI include **fairness, accountability, transparency, and data privacy**. The strategy also highlights the importance of intellectual property protection, suggesting IP facilitation centers and training for relevant authorities, and emphasizes the need for India to release a strategy paper to establish its leadership role in the evolving AI landscape, considering the policy initiatives of other countries.

TRAI Consultation Paper (2022)

In 2022, the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) released a [consultation paper](#) on 'Leveraging Artificial Intelligence and Big Data in Telecommunication Sector'.

Figure 2: AI policy and strategy timeline as per the TRAI paper

In line with NITI’s Responsible AI use principles, TRAI recommended the establishment of an **independent, statutory regulatory authority and a risk-based framework** for sensitive use cases. The authority would ‘evolve the framework based on its assessment, advice of proposed MSB (*multi-stakeholder body; italics ours*), global best practices, and public consultation, ensuring that principles of responsible AI are made applicable at each phase of AI framework lifecycle like design, development, validation, deployment, monitoring and refinement’.

India AI 2023 Expert Group Report (2023)

In October 2023, 7 working groups set up by India’s Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY) submitted a [comprehensive report](#) on the ‘vision, objectives, outcomes, and design’ of India’s AI strategy.

It stated that the MEITy had begun implementing the 'National Program on AI'. The program had four components: **Data Management Office, National Centre for AI, Skilling on AI, and Responsible AI**. 'IndiaAI' complemented the 'National Program on AI' by addressing gaps in the AI ecosystem. It used a mission-centric approach to address gaps in the AI ecosystem. These gaps include compute infrastructure, data, AI financing, research and innovation, targeted skilling, and institutional capacity for data. The initiative aimed to maximize AI's potential to advance India's progress.

Each working group dealt with an important aspect of India’s AI strategy:

1. Centres of excellence to promote research, knowledge sharing, and commercialization of IP
2. The architecture of India's dataset platform, as a platform-as-a-service (PaaS) or architecture-as-a-service (AaaS) for various organizations
3. Institutional capacity and the draft National Data Governance Policy under an independent authority
4. Pro-innovation collaborative infrastructure building for future AI startups in India
5. Educational, research and curricular interventions for AI upskilling
6. Overview of compute capacity– use cases, evaluations, markets and open-source, security and UI, and management, etc.
7. Technical capabilities, latency, and specifications of semicon chips, including financial incentives and infra support for deployment

EAC-PM Working Paper (2024)

Authors affiliated with the Economic Advisory Council to the Prime Minister (EAC-PM) **independently** published a [working paper](#) on AI regulation using a **complex adaptive system (CAS)** approach. It emphasizes the following key principles:

- **Instituting Guardrails and Partitions:** The CAS approach advocates for establishing clear boundary conditions, known as "Guardrails," to limit undesirable AI behaviors. Additionally, creating "Partitions" within AI systems helps prevent systemic failures by acting as barriers to dysfunction. This is akin to setting up firebreaks in forests to contain potential wildfires.
- **Ensuring Human Control through Manual 'Overrides' and 'Authorization Chokepoints':** Critical infrastructure should incorporate mechanisms for human intervention at key stages to address erratic AI behaviors. Manual overrides empower humans to intervene when necessary, maintaining human agency in decision-making processes. Multi-factor authentication authorization protocols provide robust checks before executing high-risk actions, requiring consensus from multiple credentialed individuals.
- **Transparency and Explainability:** The CAS-based framework stresses the importance of transparency in AI systems. Open licensing of core algorithms for external audits, AI factsheets, and continuous monitoring of AI systems are crucial for ensuring accountability. Periodic mandatory audits enhance transparency and explainability, allowing for external scrutiny of AI operations.
- **Distinct Accountability:** The CAS approach calls for establishing distinct lines of accountability and predefined liability protocols to ensure responsible deployment of AI technologies. This includes holding individuals or entities responsible for the outcomes of AI systems and processes.

- **Specialized, Agile Regulatory Body**: A specialized, agile regulatory body is essential for effectively regulating AI technologies. This regulatory body should adapt quickly to advancements in AI, continuously monitor AI systems, maintain a national registry for regulatory compliance, and foster innovation. The dynamic nature of this regulatory body allows for real-time recalibration of regulations to keep pace with technological progress.

These proposed contours of AI regulation using a complex adaptive system approach differ from traditional regulatory frameworks in several ways:

- **Real-time Guardrails vs. Predictive Approaches**: The CAS approach focuses on instituting real-time guardrails rather than attempting to predict outcomes, acknowledging the unpredictable nature of AI systems. Traditional regulatory frameworks often rely on ex-ante impact analysis and risk assessment, which may not be sustainable for regulating complex and evolving technologies like AI.
- **Human Control and Accountability**: The CAS approach emphasizes the critical role of human control in AI governance, advocating for manual overrides, authorization chokepoints, and distinct accountability lines. This human-centric approach ensures that individuals retain oversight and responsibility for AI actions, which may not be as explicitly emphasized in traditional regulatory frameworks.
- **Transparency and Explainability**: The CAS-based framework places a strong emphasis on transparency and explainability in AI systems, promoting open licensing of core algorithms, AI factsheets, and external audits. This focus on transparency is essential for ensuring accountability and building trust in AI technologies, which may not be as rigorously enforced in traditional regulatory frameworks.

[Short critique of the CAS approach](#)

Bhashini

[Bhashini](#) is an effort housed within the National Language Translation Mission of the Ministry of Electronics and IT, Government of India. It is an ‘orchestrator’ that aims to bring together a wide range of industry-academia-government collaborators under the mission and vision of seamless translation across India’s languages. This will strengthen various forms of public service delivery and communication through the country’s growing digital public infrastructure.

[AI4Bharat](#), a research laboratory at the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Madras, is one of the collaborators in this endeavor. The lab is dedicated to creating freely accessible resources for Indian languages, including datasets, tools, models, and applications. In recent years, AI4Bharat has made significant advancements in Indian language technology, which have been recognized and presented at leading international conferences. The lab's commitment to open source allows various stakeholders, such as students, researchers, businesses, government agencies, and startups, to freely utilize their models, tools, datasets, and applications.

Industry/Tech Groups

People+AI

Tanuj Bhojwani, who heads the nonprofit [People+AI](#), argues for an AI strategy for ‘[Adbhut India](#)’ (‘Adbhut’ is Hindi for ‘Amazing’) that puts the Indian people at the center of its mission. People+AI is funded by philanthropists who also helped set up India’s digital public infrastructure (DPI)– Nandan Nilekani, Pramod Verma, et al. According to Bhojwani:

1. For the levels of intelligence we need for transformative AI, we need to create much more data than we have right now
2. The real asset is compute
3. India has a lot of latent demand for AI
4. Given its democratic setup, young population, and tech and startup ecosystem, India is ready for AI
5. India will be a large market for AI use cases, given shifting business model(s)
6. The Indian strategy, therefore, will comprise open datasets, data-collection infrastructure, open-source pre-trained models, task-specific benchmarks, investments in compute infra, and investments in talent

This view frames Indian socioeconomic heterogeneity and institutional complexity as a market opportunity for testing and scaling AI use cases, and creating new businesses on top of the existing internet, telecom, and digital public infrastructures. To encourage this process, stakeholders would need to solve for challenges in defining problems, unequal access, compute costs, talent, policy frameworks, and long-term alignment. People+AI seeks to build a collaborative ecosystem of stakeholders to create ‘inclusive, equitable & responsible AI’. Their [action plan](#) for 2024 is accessible here.

NASSCOM Responsible AI

The National Association of Software and Service Companies (NASSCOM), a non-governmental advocacy group, released a [report](#) in 2023 on responsible AI guidelines for social good, on the research, development and use of GenAI solutions. It identifies harms such as the proliferation of mis(/dis)information, infringement of intellectual property, infringement of privacy, propagation of sociopolitical biases, cybersecurity threats, large carbon and water footprints, and labor market disruptions. To effectively address these, stakeholders should demonstrate ‘reasonable caution and foresight’ about contingencies, ‘transparency and accountability’ by disclosing their values and interests and describing datasets and methodologies, and ‘reliability and safety’ in adhering to standards and compliance.

Think Tanks

Takshashila Institute

In their first discussion [paper](#) on the AI governance approach in India, researchers at Takshashila underline that India must think about AI from a national interest perspective. Its power to improve governance and essential services in low-income countries can potentially be blunted by regulation that concentrates its development with a few players. The paper emphasizes individual rights to the control and distribution of data, and corresponding training of algorithms on data from target populations to remove bias. It leans towards a market-based, pro-innovation approach in terms of cloud (storage) and computing infrastructure, such that more and more players can enter a competitive market to offer different kinds of services. Risk management through a risk-based framework comes in when tackling 'high-stakes AI applications' as opposed to encouraging general innovation in other areas.

In another [report](#) on the current state of hardware capabilities in India, the authors cover the following-

“Three recent trends in the semiconductor and AI industries warrant a comprehensive AI hardware policy in India:

- A gradual transition from manufacturing general-purpose to application-specific hardware around the world
- The improved cost-benefit ratio for India to focus on the development of inference-related AI chips
- Emerging alternatives to ARM processor architectures which can handle AI workload better and more efficiently

From an Indian semiconductor and AI perspective, the current ecosystem can be analysed in the following aspects:

- Strengths include semiconductor design expertise and the rise in domestic IP related to AI applications
- Weaknesses are poor R&D ecosystem, supply chain infrastructure and the current investment climate
- Opportunities are the multiplier effects that AI hardware possesses in providing policy solutions for critical sectors
- Threats include the head start that the US and China have gotten in the AI hardware race and prospective regulations on the use of AI in specific applications

If an AI hardware policy is implemented in the country, policy priorities should include,

- A dedicated trailing edge fab that handles AI inference chip manufacturing
- Supporting and funding open source projects specifically related to AI hardware design
- Expanding existing manufacturing and design policy schemes to include AI hardware development
- International collaboration, especially with the US and Quad, to integrate AI hardware at the multilateral stage”

Observer Research Foundation

ORF released a [paper](#) on the challenges to AI governance in India. Among key problems that policymakers must contend with, the paper identified

The document provides several recommendations for strengthening the AI ecosystem in India:

- **Education and Awareness**: It is recommended to educate users and stakeholders about the promises and perils of generative AI. Awareness campaigns led by the government, media, private sector, and civil society can significantly contribute to enhancing understanding and awareness of AI technologies.
- **Regulatory Framework**: Determining which parts of the AI tech stack need to be regulated and considering sectoral or risk-based approaches is crucial. The report suggests that AI systems should accommodate human interventions to strengthen checks and balances rather than relying solely on automation.
- **Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)**: Collaborations between governments, the private sector, and civil society organizations under PPPs can support AI governance initiatives. These partnerships can help execute industry self-regulation measures, form AI ethics advisory boards, co-design AI policies, and enhance public-sector adoption of AI. Training data collaborations are also highlighted as important for addressing AI biases.
- **Flexibility in Regulations**: The report emphasizes the need for flexibility in AI regulations, considering the rapidly evolving nature of AI technology. Regulations should focus less on minor use cases and primarily target large conglomerates that have the potential to cause widespread harm. Drawing on existing national technology policies and incorporating relevant features from international initiatives like the OECD AI Principles, the EU AI Act, and the G7 Guiding Principles can help in framing appropriate AI laws for India.
- **Strengthening the Five Pillars of the AI Ecosystem**: To fortify India's AI ecosystem, the document suggests focusing on academia, startups, policymakers and government institutions, and multinational corporations. Recommendations include incorporating AI into university curricula, incentivizing startups to develop homegrown AI applications, ensuring AI literacy among policymakers, and integrating the perspectives of multinational corporations in AI regulatory processes.

Carnegie India

Further from its Global Technology Summit, Carnegie India launched a series of articles on AI in India:

Despite the lack of a coherent framework to manage risks, [India's AI strategy](#) has 3 key elements: data, compute, and models.

India recognizes the potential of data as a catalyst for innovation and has taken steps to encourage the **sharing of anonymized data** for public benefit. The country has developed

technical protocols for "data empowerment" and drafted national policies to support this goal. A recently enacted personal data protection law in India incorporates key privacy principles while excluding publicly available personal data from its scope, potentially enabling the use of such data for training AI models.

However, the country faces a significant challenge in the **lack of structured data** in local Indian languages, leading to issues of **bias** and underrepresentation in AI systems. To address this, India should prioritize initiatives that improve the accessibility of digital content. Additionally, the country should **collaborate with other nations** on data sharing to ensure that foundational AI models accurately represent Indian culture.

Regarding computing power, or "compute," India's plans to enhance its capabilities may encounter obstacles related to capital, labor, and infrastructure. These challenges arise from the **high cost of advanced GPUs, a shortage of skilled labor, and market concentration with labs based in the West**. To maintain uninterrupted AI-led innovation, India should focus on developing a "compute stack" that is scalable, self-sufficient, and sustainable. As a starting point, policymakers should assess India's current compute capacity and projected needs to inform strategies on incentivizing and locally manufacturing specific types of semiconductors.

Discussions at the GTS highlight an emerging debate on whether India should pursue its national AI objectives through **small, open-source models tailored** for specific use cases or through proprietary, general-purpose, compute-intensive models, which are mostly of foreign origin. The consensus suggests that both open-source and proprietary models will have a place in India's AI future. Some technologists argue that small, open-source models trained on relevant datasets will be suitable for proposed applications in India, while others believe that closed-source systems may be more appropriate for military applications and other sovereign purposes. India has historically taken a **strong stance** on this issue, announcing an official policy in 2014 to encourage the adoption of open-source software in government organizations. Whether this policy will extend to AI systems remains an important strategic decision for the country.

Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy

Vidhi's [Ameen Jauhar](#) notes that given the government has set no final date by which it will enact the seemingly all-encompassing Digital India Act (a revamped version of the IT Act, 2000), India might adopt a model that is unlike both the EU and the US. Specifically:

“India will steer clear from both the EU and US models, thus, *ruling out any omnibus AI law, or targeted regulation of certain high-risk use cases of AI (Italics ours)*, respectively. Instead, the DIA will seek to **codify responsible AI principles** which were published by NITI Aayog in 2021, and transform them into specific legal obligations. It is also likely that with these overarching codification of obligations, there will be **greater nuance through sectoral regulations**, as well as industry guidelines and standards, especially on safety (like minimizing bias, false positives and false negatives, and promoting transparency in design and development).”

Key Indian AI Actors

Policymakers

- Rajeev Chandrasekhar - Minister of State for Electronics & IT ([MEITY](#)) and Skill Development, directly overseeing national AI initiatives
- Amitabh Kant - [G20 Sherpa](#) and former CEO of NITI Aayog who drove the early 'AI for All' strategy
- Dr. Ajay Kumar Sood - Principal Scientific Advisor. [Office of the Principal Scientific Advisor](#), aided by the Prime Minister's Science, Technology, and Innovation Advisory Council (PM-STIAC)
- Shombi Sharp - [UN Resident Coordinator in India](#) who advocates AI for sustainable development goals
- Ajay Sawhney - Former IT Secretary who convened multi-stakeholder consultations on India's AI strategy
- Rajiv Kumar - Former Vice Chairman of NITI Aayog, pushed for AI adoption in governance
- NITI Aayog - Apex government think tank that developed the National AI Strategy
- EAC PM - Niche advisory council on economic policy that sits at NITI
- TRAI
- NASSCOM

Academia & Research

- IITs (Indian Institutes of Technology) - Premier engineering institutions, many with dedicated AI research groups, e.g. IIT Madras (Robert Bosch Center for Data Science & AI), IIT Delhi, IIT Bombay, IIT Kharagpur, IIT Hyderabad
- IISc (Indian Institute of Science), Bengaluru - Top-ranked Indian research university with an AI lab
- IIIT Hyderabad - Key player in India's language AI efforts, developed many public datasets
- Private Universities - Entities like BITS Pilani, Amity University investing in AI research and education
- TCS Research - Research wing of India's largest IT firm TCS, works on AI for multiple domains
- Adobe Research India - Bengaluru lab of Adobe funding research into computer vision, NLP etc.

- Microsoft Research India - Bengaluru lab working on AI for accessibility, healthcare, education etc.
- Google Research India - Bengaluru center with teams working on AI, led by prominent researcher Manish Gupta
- IBM Research India - Bengaluru lab working on trustworthy AI, infra, applying AI for social good
- Accenture Labs Bengaluru - Focuses on applied AI in Accenture's key verticals like financial services

Think Tanks & Civil Society

- iSPIRT - Tech policy think tank that has recommended treating data as a 'national resource' to boost AI ecosystem
- Wadhvani AI - Nonprofit institute developing open-source AI solutions for social good in health, agriculture etc.
- Aapti Institute - Bengaluru think tank researching governance frameworks for data and AI
- Tandem Research - Goa-based interdisciplinary research collective studying social implications of AI
- Observer Research Foundation (ORF) - Independent think tank, has published reports on India's AI strategy
- Carnegie India - Indian affiliate of Carnegie Endowment, convenes track 2 dialogues on AI policy
- Dialogue - Public policy think tank driving multi-stakeholder conversations on AI governance

Overall, India has articulated high ambitions to be an 'AI garage for the world', seeking to develop and deploy AI at a population scale for inclusive development. There is substantial public and private investment underway to build indigenous AI capabilities across research, skills, data, and compute layers. The government has also initiated a multi-stakeholder process to develop a comprehensive AI strategy balancing innovation and risk management.

However, significant challenges remain for India to realize its AI potential, requiring coordinated effort across different sectors and stakeholders:

- Boosting core research in AI and reducing dependence on foreign models, tools, and hardware
- Developing a robust domestic semiconductor and electronics manufacturing ecosystem

- Sustaining political will and institutional capacity to drive a whole-of-government approach to AI
- Addressing structural issues of digital literacy, access, and inclusion to ensure AI benefits all
- Managing geopolitical tensions and partnerships to secure India's strategic interests
- Crafting appropriate governance frameworks to promote responsible development and use of AI
- Deepening public understanding and trust in AI based on India's democratic ethos

These challenges also play into challenges for field-building in AI safety:

- Civil society groups may perceive an emphasis on x-risks as harmful to drawing public attention to near-term risks such as privacy, surveillance, and misinformation
- Government work proves to be a double-edged sword: superficially supportive, but ultimately dismissive of AI safety risks
- The VC/startup/research ecosystem in India suspects AI safety work as harmful to AI development for business and social solutions
- Specific interest groups might not align with/understand the goals of AI safety work
- Global partners/stakeholders (funders, AI safety research groups, etc.) remain skeptical of the role of India in managing AI x-risks

What next?

Immediate Steps [1-3 months]

- Receive at least 3 rounds of feedback on this document from professionals in communities associated with EA, EA in India, AI safety, and AI in India
- Understand the degrees of influence aforementioned key stakeholders exercise over the policymaking process, via expert interviews
- Publish this document as a post on the EA Forum

Long-term Steps [3-5 months]

- Convene accessible, community-wide dialogues on AI safety in India, to elicit discussions on strategic postures in policy and advocacy, risk management approaches, and solving coordination and knowledge infrastructure problems. (Inspired by Alexander Saeri's [post](#) on similar efforts in Australia)
- Build relationships with think tanks and government institutions/policymakers to influence discourse on AI safety, especially from x-risks. (Inspired partly by resources in [AIM's new guide](#) to launching policy nonprofits)
- Create interventions in public discourse through writing/speaking engagements for Indian news channels/publications/dailies on AI safety-related topics
- Help scale up Impact Academy's own talent and community-building initiatives for technical and governance AI safety in India